

Potentiality of the new products as carcinostats is under investigation and shall be reported elsewhere.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected.

α -(*p*-NN-bis-2'-Cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)- γ -phenyl)- $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -butenolide (I, R=R₁=R₂=R₃=H). *General method*: An intimate mixture of β -benzoylpropionic acid¹⁸ (0.35 g), 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde¹⁹ (0.25 g), fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride (1 ml) was placed in a round bottomed flask with an air condenser. The contents were heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. The orange-yellow crystals were washed with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 76.8%, m.p. 173°. (Found: N, 11.89. C₂₈H₁₉O₂N₂ requires N, 11.38%). IR absorption spectrum (KBr) shows characteristic band of $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -butenolide ring at 1770 cm⁻¹ and tertiary-N at 1320 cm⁻¹.

2-Hydroxy-1,2-diphenyl-4-(*p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-pyrrolidone (II, R = H): The butenolide (I, 1; 0.37 g) and redistilled aniline (0.1 g) were taken in a 50 ml round bottomed flask fitted with an air condenser and heated for 3 hr on a steam bath. The contents were cooled and acidified with aqueous hydrochloric acid when 2-hydroxy-1,2-diphenyl-4-(*p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-pyrrolidone separated as solid. Recrystallisation from ethanol gave light yellow needles of the product, yield 63.4%, m.p. 215°. (Found; N, 12.56. C₂₉H₂₀O₂N₄ requires N, 12.12%).

Other pyrrolidones (8 to 18) were prepared in a similar way.

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Sorption Behaviour of Th⁴⁺, ZrO²⁺, UO₂²⁺ and Some Rare Earths on Collidinium Molybdoarsenate—Separation of Th⁴⁺

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THE insoluble salts of heteropolyacids are preferred to other inorganic ion exchangers as they usually exhibit selective ion exchange behaviour¹⁻³. However, the most widely used heteropolyacid salts, ammonium molybdo- and tungsto-phosphates, show dispersion tendency and need foreign support material for column operation^{4,5}. The present communication reports the sorption behaviour of UO₂²⁺, ZrO²⁺, Th⁴⁺ and some rare earths on a highly insoluble exchanger, collidinium molybdoarsenate (CMA)⁶, whose column has been successfully used for the separation of Th⁴⁺.

Experimental

Reagents and materials :

Collidinium molybdoarsenate, (C₈H₁₁NH)₈-Mo₁₂AsO₄₀ (CMA), was prepared as described earlier⁶. All metal salts used were of AR grade. The radiotracers ¹³⁴Cs, ⁸⁶Rb, ⁸⁸⁺⁸⁹Sr, ^{114m}+¹¹⁴In, ¹⁴¹Ce, ¹⁶⁰Tb and ⁹¹Y were obtained from B.A.R.C., Bombay.

Apparatus and procedure :

A well type scintillation counter was used for activity measurements of tracers except ⁹¹Y whose activity was determined on a G.M. counter⁷. UO₂²⁺ and ZrO²⁺ were determined spectrophotometrically⁸, whereas La³⁺ and Th⁴⁺ by EDTA titrations⁹. The distribution coefficient values (K_d) for various metals were determined and separation of Th⁴⁺ was carried on the column of the exchanger in the manner already described⁶.

Results and Discussion

It is seen from Table 1 that CMA shows affinity for ZrO²⁺, Th⁴⁺ and UO₂²⁺ in the order Th⁴⁺>

$ZrO^{2+} > UO_2^{2+}$. To investigate the probable sorption mechanism and to work out conditions for the elution of the ions on the column of the exchanger, the variation of K_d values for ZrO^{2+} , Th^{4+} and UO_2^{2+} as a function of nitric acid concentration has been investigated. The data is reported in terms of

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENT VALUES (K_d) for Th^{4+} , ZrO^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} AND RARE EARTH CATIONS ($0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) ON CMA EXCHANGER AT pH 3

Metal ion	Taken as	K_d (cm^3/g)	Metal ion	Taken as	K_d (cm^3/g)
Th^{4+}	Nitrate	C.A.	Ce^{3+}	Ammonium nitrate	0
ZrO^{2+}	Chloride	1567	La^{3+}	Oxide	0
UO_2^{2+}	Acetate	1100	Y^{3+}	Oxide	0
Tb^{3+}	Oxide	3			

C.A. = Complete adsorption.

$\log K_d$ vs $\log [HNO_3]$ plots in Fig. 1. It is seen from Fig. 1 that K_d values of Th^{4+} and ZrO^{2+} are not significantly affected up to 0.01 mol dm^{-3} nitric acid and Th^{4+} is completely adsorbed in lower nitric acid concentrations. For both Th^{4+} and ZrO^{2+} ,

Fig. 1. Variation in K_d of UO_2^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} and Th^{4+} ($10^{-3} M$) on CMA with HNO_3 concentration.

the slope of the lines in the nitric acid concentration range of 0.01 to 1 mol dm^{-3} does not correspond to the charge of the cation showing thereby that sorption of Th^{4+} does not proceed through ion exchange mechanism. In case of $Zr(IV)$, on the basis of slope it is not possible to say whether sorption proceeds through ion exchange or not because other cationic species^{10,11} of $Zr(IV)$ in addition to ZrO^{2+} may be present. A mixture of various zirconium species will give rise to unknown slope in the above plot. UO_2^{2+} ions are adsorbed in low acid concentrations on this exchanger and the slope (~ -1) of the straight line shows the possibility of its being adsorbed as UO_2OH^+ species. Similar findings are also reported in case of ammonium molybdophosphate by Ganzerli *et al*¹². These plots further

show that UO_2^{2+} ions can be separated from ZrO^{2+} and Th^{4+} on the column of this exchanger as it is least strongly adsorbed. It is further inferred that ZrO^{2+} and Th^{4+} ions can be separated from all other ions, including those studied previously⁶, except Tl^+ . Representative binary separations of Th^{4+} from Cs^+ , Rb^+ , Sr^{2+} , In^{3+} and Tb^{3+} were actually carried out on the column. Th^{4+} was eluted out by 1 : 1 mixture of 2 mol dm^{-3} collidinium nitrate and nitric acid. All other ions are eluted with 0.01 mol dm^{-3} hydrochloric acid. Recoveries are 100% in all cases except for In^{3+} , which is 98%. Details of separations achieved are given in Table 2. These studies can be utilized in the recovery of pure thorium from its ores.

TABLE 2—BINARY SEPARATION OF 232 μg OF Th^{4+} ON THE COLUMN OF COLLIDINIUM MOLYBDOARSENATE FROM OTHER METAL IONS

Th^{4+} was eluted completely with 4 cm^3 1 : 1 mixture of 2 mol dm^{-3} collidinium nitrate and nitric acid. Eluent for other ions was 0.01 mol dm^{-3} hydrochloric acid.

Metal ion	Amount taken (μg)	Volume of eluent at elution peak (cm^3)	Metal ion	Amount taken (μg)	Volume of eluent at elution peak (cm^3)
Cs^+	1330	2	In^{3+}	459	4
Rb^+	855	4	Tb^{3+}	636	4
Sr^{2+}	2000	4			

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